

USING THE PRINCIPLE OF INTERDISCIPLINARY RELATIONSHIP IN STUDYING DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS IN SPECIALIZED SCHOOLS AND ACADEMIC LYCEUMS

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Abstract: In this article, experiments are written on how to use the principle of interdisciplinarity calculated from the didactic principles of teaching in the teaching of the differential equations section of the mathematics course of specialized schools and academic lyceums.

Key words: differential equation, interdisciplinarity, speed, acceleration, general solution, particular solution, physical problem, chemical problem, economic problem.

Ma'lumki, so'nggi yillarda respublikamizda matematika ta'limini yanada takomillashtirishga katta ahamiyat berilmoqda. Chunki fan va texnika jadal suratlar bilan rivojlanib borayotgan bugungi kunda har qanday mutaxassis o'z faoliyatida matematika va matematik metodlarga tez-tez murojaat qiladi. Shuning uchun ham bugungi kunda barcha ta'lim muassasalarida, jumladan ixtisoslashgan maktablar va akademik litseylarda matematikani o'qitishga katta ahamiyat berilishi, ya'ni matematik ta'lim jarayonini yangi pedagogic texnologiyalar hamda axborot kommunikatsion texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda tashkil qilish asosiy vazifalaridan biriga aylandi.

Ixtisoslashgan maktablar va akademik litseylarda matematika darslarini tashkil qilishda o'qitishning didaktik tamoyillaridan ham muntazam foydalanish kerak. Didaktik tamoyillar ta'lim nazariyasining asosini tashkil qiladi. Shuning

uchun o‘quv materialini tushuntirish metodlarini tanlashda ta’lim nazariyasi tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan didaktik tamoyillarga amal qilish kerak. Bu didaktik tamoyillar ichida fanlararo aloqadorlik tamoyili muhim o‘ringa ega. Shuning uchun ham biz ushbu maqolada differensial tenglamalar mavzusini o‘qitish jarayonida fanlararo aloqadorlik tamoyilidan foydalanish bo‘yicha fikrlarimizni bayon qilamiz.

Ma’lumki, fizika, iqtisodiyot, biologiya, kimyo, tibbiyot va bir qator texnika fanlarida uchraydigan ko‘plab jarayonlar differensial tenglamalar yordamida tavsiflanadi. Shu tenglamalarni o‘rganishi bilan tegishli jarayonlar haqida biror ma’lumotga, tasavvurga ega bo‘lamiz. O‘sha differensial tenglamalar o‘rganilayotgan jarayonning matematik modelidan iborat bo‘ladi. Bu model qanchalik mukammal bo‘lsa, differensial tenglamalarni o‘rganish natijasida olingan ma’lumotlar jarayonlarni shunchalik to‘la tavsiflaydi. Bu aytilganlardan differensial tenglamalar mavzusi fanlararo aloqadorlik tamoyilidan foydalanish uchun katta imkoniyatga ega ekanligini ko‘ramiz.

Ma’lumki, funksiya, xosila, integral kabi bir qator tushunchalarni kiritilishiga amaliyotning bir qator masalalarini yechish turtki bo‘lgani kabi differensial tenglama tushunchasini kiritishga ham fan va texnikaning turli masalalarini yechish turtki bo‘lgan. Quyida biz bu masalalardan namunalar keltiramiz.

1- masala. Massasi m ga teng bo‘lgan jism v_0 boshlang‘ich tezlik bilan biror balandlikdan tashlab yuborilgan. Jism tezligini o‘zgarish qonunini toping (1-chizma).

Yechimi: Nyutonning ikkinchi qonuniga asosan:

$$F = ma = m \frac{dv}{dt},$$

bu yerda F -jismga ta’sir etayotgan kuchlarning yig‘indisi (teng ta’sir etuvchisi). Jismga faqat ikkita kuch ta’sir etishi mumkin deb hisoblaylik:

1-chizma

Havoning qarshilik kuchi $F_1 = -kv$, $k > 0$; yerning tortishish kuchi $F_2 = mg$.

Shunday qilib, matematik nuqtayi nazardan F kuch

a) F_2 ga; b) F_1 ga; c) $F_1 + F_2$ ga teng bo'lishi mumkin.

a) $F = F_2$ bo'lsin. Unda birinchi tartibli $m \frac{dv}{dt} = mg$ differensial tenglamaga ega bo'lamiz. Bundan $\frac{dv}{dt} = g$ yoki $v_1 = gt + c$ (c – o'zgarmas son) kelib chiqadi.

Agar $v(0) = v_0$ ni e'tiborga olsak, $c = v_0$ bo'ladi. Bu holda izlangan qonun $v_1(t) = gt + v_0$ dan iborat bo'ladi.

b) $F = F_1$ bo'lsa, $m \frac{dv}{dt} = -kv$ bo'lib, bundan $v(t) = v_0 e^{-\frac{k}{m}t}$ kelib chiqadi.

c) $F = F_1 + F_2$ bo'lsin. Bu holda $m \frac{dv}{dt} = mg - kv$ ($k > 0$) differensial tenglamaga kelamiz. Bundan quyidagini topamiz.

$$v(t) = c_0 e^{-\frac{k}{m}t} + \frac{mg}{k}; \quad v(0) = v_0, \quad v_2(t) = \left(v_0 - \frac{mg}{k}\right) e^{-\frac{k}{m}t} + \frac{mg}{k}$$

Bu masala fizik mazmundagi masala bo'lib, uni yechish jarayonida o'qituvchi o'quvchilar bilan fizikadan ma'lum bo'lgan Nyutonning ikkinchi qonuni $F=ma$, jismning tezlanishi $a = \frac{dv}{dt}$, jismning tezligi $v = \frac{ds}{dt}$ lar haqida hamda kuchlarni qo'shish va ikki kuchning teng ta'sir etuvchisi tushunchalarini takrorlaydi.

Buning natijasida o'quvchilarda differensial tenglama tushunchasi bilan fizikadagi tushunchalar orasidagi bog'lanish bo'yicha bilimlar mustahkamlanadi.

2-masala. Bozorda t vaqt o‘tishi bilan biror mahsulot narxi $P(t)$, unga talab $h(t)$ va taklif $s(t)$ funksiyalar bo‘yicha o‘zgarib boradi. Narx funksiyasi, talab va taklif funksiyalari orasidagi bog‘lanish topilsin.

Yechish: Bozor qonuniyatlariga asosan Δt vaqt oralig‘ida narxning o‘sishi Δp talabni taklifdan qanchalik darajada kattaligiga va shu vaqt oralig‘iga to‘g‘ri proporsional bo‘ladi. Agar proporsionallik koeffitsenti k bo‘lsa, bu qonuniyatni matematik ko‘rinishda ifodalab, undan quyidagilarga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta p &= k(h - s)\Delta t \Rightarrow \frac{\Delta p}{\Delta t} = k(h - s) \Rightarrow \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta p}{\Delta t} = \lim k(h - s) \Rightarrow p' \\ &= k(h - s)\end{aligned}$$

Demak, $p' = k(h - s)$ tenglik $p = p(t)$ narx funksiyasiga nisbatan eng soddalik differensial tenglama bo‘lib, undan

$$p(t) = k \int [h(t) - s(t)] dt$$

Bu masala iqtisodiy mazmundagi masala bo‘lib, uni yechish jarayonida o‘quvchilar mahsulot narxi, talab, taklif kabi iqtisodiy tushunchalar bilan tanishadilar. Bu esa ularda iqtisodiyot bilan matematika orasidagi fanlararo aloqadorlikni tushunib yetishlari uchun asosiy omil bo‘ladi.

3-masala. Matematik mayatnikning harakat tenglamasi keltirib chiqarilsin.

Yechish: Vertikal tekislikda yotgan l radiusli k aylana bo‘ylab og‘irlik kuchi ta’siri ostida harakat qiluvchi m massaga ega bo‘lgan P nuqta matematik mayatnikni tasvirlaydi (2-chizma). Har bir momentda P nuqtaning o‘rni $\varphi(t)$ burchak bilan to‘la aniqlanadi. Masalaning sharti bo‘yicha P nuqta faqat og‘irlik kuchi ta’siri ostida harakatlanadi. Ammo bu harakatda aylananing roli bor. P nuqta aylana bo‘ylab harakat qilishga majbur etadi, ya’ni P nuqtaga ichki normal bo‘yicha yo‘nalgan F kuch ta’sir etadi. Agar tortish kuchi mg ni ikkita tashkil etuvchiga ajratsak, ular $F_1 = -mg \sin \varphi$, $F_2 = -mg \cos \varphi$ va bu holda $F_3 + F_2 = 0$ bo‘ladi. Shunday qilib, P ga ta’sir etayotgan kuchlarning teng ta’sir etuvchisi $F = F_1 + F_2 + F_3 = F_1 = -mg \sin \varphi$. Demak, P nuqtaning harakat tenglamasi

Nyutonning ikkinchi qonuniga asosan

$ml\varphi'' = -mgsin\varphi$ yoki $l\varphi'' + gsin\varphi = 0$ ko'rinishda bo'ladi.

2-chizma

Bu masalani yechish ikkinchi tartibli differensial tenglamaga olib keldi. Uni yechish jarayonida fizika kursidagi matematik mayatnik, tortishish kuchi, teng ta'sir etuvchi kuch va Nyutonning ikkinchi qonunidan foydalanildi. Bu esa matematika bilan fizika fani orasidagi fanlararo aloqadorlikni anglatadi.

4-masala. O'zgarmas a tezlanish bilan to'g'ri chiziqli harakat qilayotgan moddiy nuqtaning harakat qonuni topilsin.

Yechish: Masalani yechish t vaqtning funksiyasidan iborat bo'lgan $s = s(t)$ formulani topishdan iborat. Masalaning shartiga asosan $\frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = a$ yoki $s''(t) = a$ ikkinchi tartibli differensial tenglamani tuzamiz. Ketma-ket integrallash orqali tenglamani yechamiz.

$$s' = at + c_1, \quad s = \frac{at^2}{2} + c_1t + c_2$$

c_1 va c_2 larni topish uchun $s|_{t=t_0} = s_0$ va $s'|_{t=t_0} = v_0$ boshlang'ich shartlardan foydalanamiz. Ularga asosan $v_0 = at_0 + c_1$ dan $c_1 = v_0 - at_0$ ni

$$s_0 = \frac{at_0^2}{2} + c_1t_0 + c_2 \text{ yoki } s_0 = \frac{at_0^2}{2} + (v_0 - at_0)t_0 + c_2 \text{ dan esa}$$

$$c_2 = s_0 - v_0t_0 + \frac{at_0^2}{2}$$

ni topamiz. Topilganlardan foydalanib quyidagi harakat qonunini topamiz:

$$s(t) = s_0 + v_0(t - t_0) + \frac{a(t-t_0)^2}{2}.$$

Bu masala ham fizik mazmundagi masaladir. Uni yechish jarayonida fizika kursidan ma'lum bo'lgan tezlik, tezlanish va harakat qonun kabi tushunchalariga murojaat qilinadi.

5-masala. Agar kimyoviy reaksiya A va B moddaning har biri o'tadigan C moddaning miqdori x ga teng bo'lsa, u holda o'zgarish temperaturada va boshqa ba'zi shartlar bajarilganda reaksiya tezligi $\frac{dx}{dt}$ quyidagilarga proporsional bo'ladi:

1) A modda C moddaga o'tganda – A moddaning qolgan miqdoriga; bunda ushbu differensial tenglama kelib chiqadi: $\frac{dx}{dt} = k(a - x)$, bu yerda a bilan A moddaning boshlang'ich miqdori belgilangan , k-proporsionallik koeffitsenti ($k>0$);

2) A va B moddalar C moddaga o'tganda tegishli massalar ko'paytmasiga proporsional bo'ladi, bunda quyidagi differensial tenglama kelib chiqadi:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k(a - x)(b - x),$$

Bu yerda a va b lar A va B moddalarning boshlang'ich miqdori, k-proporsionallik koeffitsenti ($k>0$).

Har ikkala hol uchun x ning t vaqtga bog'lanishini topamiz. Tuzilgan differensial tenglamalar o'zgaruvchilari ajraladigan tenglamalardir. Har ikkala holda ham bir xil boshlang'ich shartga, ya'ni $t=0$ da $x=0$ ga egamiz. Birinchi holda o'zgaruvchilarni ajratgandan so'ng

$$\frac{dx}{x - a} = -k dt$$

Tenglamani hosil qilamiz. Uni yechaylik.

$$\int \frac{dx}{x - a} = -k \int dt, \ln|x - a| = -kt + c, \quad x - a = e^{-kt+c},$$

$$x = a + ce^{-kt}.$$

Boshlang'ich shartdan $c = a$ ni topamiz. Demak, xususiy yechim $x = a(1 - e^{-kt})$ ko'rinishga keladi. Bu yechimdan $t \rightarrow \infty$ da $x \rightarrow a$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Ikkinchi holda o'zgaruvchilarni ajratgandan so'ng quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\frac{dx}{(x-a)(x-b)} = kdt$$

$$\frac{1}{(x-a)(x-b)} = -\frac{1}{b-a} \left(\frac{1}{x-a} - \frac{1}{x-b} \right)$$

Ekanligini e'tiborga olib tenglamani yozamiz:

$$\int \frac{dx}{(x-a)(x-b)} = -\int \frac{1}{b-a} \left(\frac{1}{x-a} - \frac{1}{x-b} \right) dx =$$

$$= -\frac{1}{b-a} \left[\int \frac{dx}{x-a} - \int \frac{dx}{x-b} \right] = -\frac{1}{b-a} \ln \frac{x-a}{x-b}, \int kdt = kt + c.$$

Demak, $-\frac{1}{b-a} \ln \frac{x-a}{x-b} = kt + c$. Bundan $\frac{1}{b-a} \ln \frac{x-a}{x-b} = -kt + \frac{1}{b-a} \ln c$ ni yoki $\frac{x-a}{x-b} = ce^{-k(b-a)t}$ ni hosil qilamiz. Agar boshlang'ich shartni e'tiborga olsak $c = \frac{a}{b}$ bo'ladi.

$$\frac{x-a}{x-b} = \frac{a}{b} e^{-k(b-a)t}, \quad x = ab \frac{1 - e^{-k(b-a)t}}{b - ae^{-k(b-a)t}}$$

Faraz qilaylik $b > a$ bo'lsin, ya'ni B moddaning boshlang'ich miqdori A moddaning boshlang'ich miqdoridan ortiq bo'lsin. U holda buyechimdan $t \rightarrow \infty$ da $x \rightarrow a$ ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

Agar aksiga faraz qilsak, ya'ni $a > b$ desak, u holda $t \rightarrow \infty$ da $x \rightarrow b$ degan xulosaga kelamiz. Bu holda xususiy yechim quyidagicha bo'ladi:

$$x = ab \frac{e^{-k(a-b)t} - 1}{be^{-k(a-b)t} - a}$$

Bu masala kimyoviy mazmundagi masala bo'lib, uni yechish o'zgaruvchilar ajraladigan differensial tenglamaga olib keldi. Bu masalani yechish jarayonida kimyoviy reaksiyaning tezligi, kimyoviy reaksiya vaqtida bir moddaning ikkinchi moddaga o'tishi kabi tushunchalarga duch kelindi.

Shunday qilib biz, ushbu maqolada beshta masalaga to'xtaldik. Bu masalalardan

uchtasi fizik, bittasi iqtisodiy, bittasi kimyoviy mazmundagi masalalardir. Bu yerda keltirilgan va ularga o'xshash masalalarni o'qituvch ixtisoslashgan yoki akademik litseylarning yo'nalishiga qarab tanlashi mumkin. Matematika darslarida bunday masalalardan foydalanish dars jarayonida o'qitishning didaktik tamoyillaridan hisoblangan fanlararo aloqadorlik tamoyilidan foydalanishga yaqqol misol bo'la oladi. Matematika darslarini bunday tashkil qilinishi ta'lim jarayoni samarali bo'lishini ta'minlaydi.

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